

Leveraging Process Mining on the Shop Floor: An Exploratory Study - Supplementary Material

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The subsequent text offers complementary information regarding the paper "Leveraging Process Mining on the Shop Floor: An Exploratory Study".

Participant Overview

The following table presents a summary of the interview participants in this study. It provides key information about each participant, including their assigned identifier (ID), persona within their organization, industry sector, level of process mining (PM) use, and the extent of their presence on the shop floor.

ID	Persona	Industry	PM Use	Shop Floor Presence
A1	Academician	Academic/Research	Research	Project based
A2	Academician	Academic/Research	Research	Project based
I1	Expert	Consulting	Advisory	Project based
I2	Expert	Consulting	Implementation	Project based
I3	Expert	Multiple Industries	Implementation	Project based
I4	Expert	Multiple Industries	Implementation	Project based
I5	Expert	Multiple Industries	Implementation	Project based
I6	Expert	Food	No	Direct Involvement
I7	Expert	Multiple Industries	Implementation	Project based
I8	Expert	Consulting	Managerial	Project based
I9	Expert	Multiple Industries	Backend Development	Project based
I10	Expert	Multiple Industries	Implementation	Project based
I11	Expert	Automotive	Implementation	Project based
P1	Production Manager	Automotive	No	Shop Floor-Related
P2	Production Manager	Automotive	Implementation	Project based
P3	Production Manager	IoT Connectivity	No	Direct Involvement
P4	Production Manager	Rubber manufacturing	No	Direct Involvement
S1	Shopfloor	Automotive	No	Direct Involvement
S2	Shopfloor	Medical devices	No	Direct Involvement
S3	Shopfloor	Automotive	No	Direct Involvement
S4	Shopfloor	Wireless communication	No	Direct Involvement
S5	Shopfloor	Rolling Stock	No	Direct Involvement

Transition from literature to interviews

The literature analysis played a crucial role in shaping the foundation of our research despite not being explicitly highlighted in subsequent sections. After selecting the final set of 35 papers, we conducted a thorough content analysis, extracting key themes, concepts, and existing frameworks related to process mining on the shop floor. This analysis informed the development of an initial coding scheme, which served as a starting point for our interview study. The literature review also revealed gaps in current knowledge, particularly the lack of qualitative research and systematic approaches in process mining studies within manufacturing contexts, thus justifying our decision to conduct in-depth interviews.

We utilized the coding scheme derived from the literature review as a preliminary framework, which was then iteratively refined and expanded during the interview process. This approach allowed us to build upon existing knowledge while remaining open to new insights emerging from the field. Regarding the intercoder agreement, we employed a consensus-based approach where the two coders regularly met to discuss and reconcile any coding discrepancies, ensuring the analysis's consistency and reliability. This iterative coding, discussion, and refinement process continued until we reached theoretical saturation, providing a robust foundation for our findings.